

D4Science Geoportal: a framework for managing and publishing georeferenced research objects

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In the current context of Earth and Environmental Sciences, the exponential growth in the production of geospatial and temporal data makes it essential to adopt advanced tools for managing, publishing, and sharing complex information. The **D4Science Geoportal** [1] represents an innovative and versatile solution specifically designed to address these challenges. Through Virtual Research Environments (VREs) [2], it offers a comprehensive digital environment aligned with the **FAIR** principles of Open Science.

Developed as an integral part of the D4Science digital infrastructure [3], the Geoportal is an open-source framework, dedicated to the management of complex georeferenced research objects characterized by spatial, temporal and multimedia data. Its modular architecture consists of three main components: **Data-Entry**, **Data-Viewer** and **Geoportal Service**. Data-Entry (front-end) supports users in managing and publishing data. The Data-Viewer (front-end) offers tools to explore georeferenced objects through interactive maps, enriched with dynamic visualizations and temporal representations. Both modules communicate with the Geoportal Service (back-end), responsible for storing, persisting and securely accessing data, integrating with the advanced services of the D4Science infrastructure, including storage systems, geospatial servers, databases and catalogs.

The compatibility of the Geoportal with international standards defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), such as Web Map Service (WMS) and Web Feature Service (WFS), ensures interoperability and integration with other platforms and IT systems, encouraging multidisciplinary collaboration and resource sharing in distributed research areas.

One of the most significant applications of the Geoportal is the **Reef Archive Lab**, a VRE designed to support the scientific community in the study of coral reefs. This digital environment allows the management and publication of high-resolution underwater orthophotos, offering tools for annotating and cataloguing the collected data. A further important example is the **Dataset for the National Geoportal for Archaeology** (D4GNA) [4], developed for the Italian Ministry of Culture. The D4GNA manages over 1,200 archaeological excavation research projects, both nationally and internationally, promoting the standardization and digitization of archaeological documentation, and promoting the accessibility, sharing and open reuse of data.

This contribution shows how Geoportal represents an effective and replicable solution for the integrated management of geospatial, temporal and multimedia data. Designed in line

with the needs of modern research infrastructures, the Geoportal promotes interdisciplinary cooperation and innovation in the management of current environmental and cultural challenges.

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